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Bringing the European Pillar of Social Rights to Life: Lessons from four Member States

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1. Introduction

Officially proclaimed by the European Parliament, the Council and the Commission in 2017, the European Pillar of Social Rights¹ (EPSR) sets out twenty principles aimed at strengthening the social acquis of the EU by steering a process of upward social convergence across Member States. The EPSR has indeed brought about a significant relaunch of the EU's social policy agenda, in at least two respects. First, its proclamation set a new political dynamic in motion, with Jean-Claude Juncker's pledge to endow the EU with a "social triple A"². After years of focus on fiscal discipline and structural reforms, this has led to a renewed awareness of the importance of social cohesion. The EU's commitment was asserted by the following European Commission (EC) under Ursula von der Leyen's presidency. An action plan was adopted in 2021 with the aim of translating broad objectives into more specific actions and policy instruments. This, however, happened despite visible resistance from many Member States³. Second, the EPSR has put the EC back on the track of hard law initiatives pertaining to "old" as well as "new" social issues relating to pay and working conditions.

This research assesses the added value of the EPSR at the national level, shifting the focus from the adoption to

the transposition and implementation stage. It looks at three EU directives that have reached the transposition stage: the Work-Life Balance Directive (WLBD), the Transparent and Predictable Working Conditions Directive (TPWCD) and the Adequate Minimum Wages Directive (AMWD). The WLBD aims to reduce the persistent gender employment gap by encouraging fathers' participation in caregiving, thus alleviating the disproportionate care burden on women. It strengthens the existing right on parental leave, and it introduces three new rights: paternity leave, carers' leave, and flexible working arrangements (FWAs). The TPWCD extends protections to all forms of work, including precarious and non-standard employment such as zero-hour contracts, casual work, and platform work. It introduces six new material rights: limiting probationary periods to six months, granting workers the right to take up parallel employment, ensuring timely work schedule notifications, introducing safeguards against zero-hour contract abuse, allowing workers to request a transition to a more secure job, and ensuring cost-free mandatory training. The AMWD establishes a framework aimed at: improving the adequacy of statutory minimum wages in member states where the latter exists, proposing as reference values 60% of the national median wage and/ or 50% of the

¹ European Commission, Secretariat-General, (2017) European pillar of social rights. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2792/95934>

² Jean-Claude Juncker's reference to a 'social triple A' signaled his ambition for the EU to match its economic and financial strength with equally robust social standards. The term emphasized the need for high-quality employment, fair working conditions and strong social protection systems

across Member States, aiming to give the EU a top rating not just economically, but also socially (cf. Five Presidents' report)

³ At the Porto Summit, a group of nine Member States issued a "non-paper" claiming that they were supportive of a Social Europe that relies essentially on hard law (cf. [Belgian-Spanish Non Paper ahead of the Porto Social Summit](#)).

national average wage; and enhancing access of workers to minimum wage protection through collective bargaining, requiring member states to draw up national action plans to increase the collective bargaining coverage in case less than 80% of the workforce is covered by collective bargaining agreements.

The research aims (i) to assess the degree of misfit between between EU directives and pre-existing national laws in four EU member states – Belgium, Ireland, Italy and Poland – each of which represents a distinct welfare state model, (ii) to provide knowledge about the extent to which EU rights translate into higher protection of workers across member states, (iii) to shed light on the domestic political and institutional actors that mediated the implementation process, including resistance, compliance or adaptation.

II. Comparative findings

Preliminary findings show that the EPSR has catalysed an improvement of social rights across the four countries examined, either in the form of consolidation of existing rights or the creation of new rights. More specifically, we observe:

1. Tangible but uneven change.

In **12 out of 48 instances** (12 rights across the 4 countries) the transposition created new material rights, namely in Ireland (unpaid carers' leave, FWAs, parallel employment, stable form of employment, cost-free training), Italy (parallel employment, predictability of work, stable form of employment, cost-free training) and Poland (unpaid

carers' leave, stable form of employment, cost-free training).

In **11 instances existing rights were strengthened** to meet EU standards: Belgium (carers' leave, FWAs), Ireland (probationary period, adequate minimum wages), Italy (paternity leave, probationary period), Poland (parental leave, FWAs, probationary period, parallel employment, adequate minimum wages).

However, in the remaining **25 instances, EU law failed to make a breakthrough into domestic law**. This is especially striking in the case of the failure of the TPWCD to trigger change in Italy and Poland when it comes to on-demand work and predictable working conditions. We also observe notable resistance to and absence of change, especially to the provisions of the WLBD in Ireland (paternity leave, parental leave) and Italy (parental leave, FWAs), and no change to improve collective bargaining in Ireland and Poland owing to the AMWD. By contrast, in Belgium we observe minimal changes because its pre-existing legislation was largely in alignment with these EU initiatives.

2. Risk of "paper rights" without strong enforcement.

Even when transposition results in formal compliance, workers frequently lack awareness of their rights (e.g. in Ireland, Poland). Poor or lacking financial underpinning of rights (e.g. low pay during parental leave) make the take-up of certain rights unlikely or even undesirable by fathers (e.g. Ireland, Italy, Poland). Progress on the ground will depend on the political and administrative willingness to provide workers and their representatives (unions) with the necessary tools to make the use of rights effective. Examples of this are the marginal

impact of the TPWCD on working conditions for people employed on zero-hour contracts in Italy and Poland, or the failure of the AMWD to grant Irish unions a right to be heard in discussion fora with mandatory employer participation.

3. Transposition frequently becomes a second round of watering down

Since the most impactful provisions of draft directives are likely to be the more contentious ones, EU negotiations often produce compromises that deliberately leave considerable leeway for national legislators and social partners to (re)define core provisions, including levels of remuneration, definitions touching upon the scope of application, or applicable procedures, etc. This built-in ambiguity travels to the national level, where it interacts with domestic politics and institutional capacity. During the implementation process, national actors often “watered down” provisions further. The WLBD generally faced less resistance, often framed as family policy. The TPWCD and AMWD were more contested, especially raising issues of costs, labour flexibility and sovereignty, and there was greater divergence in implementation.

4. Politics matter

A key finding is that successful and ambitious implementation depends mainly on the government’s ideological platform and the power and ability of labour unions to mobilise. Case studies show that the most transformative change occurs when unions are strong, governments are supportive and administrative capacity is robust (e.g. Belgium).

In Italy and Poland, conservative and/or nationalist governments have pursued minimal, borderline-compliant transposition, precluding progressive change. In addition, the Polish unions showed a lack of interest in the transposition of the WLBD. In Ireland, political coalitions (e.g. transposition of the AMWD) and administrative capacity (e.g. implementation of the WLBD and TPWCD) limited transposition to only formal compliance with EU requirements, rather than pursuing transformative change.

III. Implications

1. Trade-off between subsidiarity and equality in EU law.

What may be useful tailoring of EU provisions for some, may look like an implementation gap to others. Thus, there is a broader dilemma when it comes to the effectiveness of hard law in enhancing social rights for all workers across Europe. The less constraining the provisions of EU law, the more flexibility Member States are granted to specify the terms in their own legal order. While this means more flexibility, in line with the principle of subsidiarity, it also implies greater differentiation of rights across the continent. Examples include:

- the absence of agreement on a European definition of “worker” (TPWCD),
- the failure to introduce a mandatory remuneration for carers’ leave (WLBD), and
- the failure to create a mandatory threshold for the minimum wage (i.e. 60% of the median wage) (AMWD).

2. Formal convergence but substantive divergence.

The current flexibility granted in implementation suggests high legal fit but low substantive fit, and fails to close the gap between workers across Member States and lead to actual upward convergence. For example, while labour markets in Ireland and Poland are highly dualized, the new rights under the TPWCD are only granted to well-protected insiders. This leeway for national decisionmakers, while necessary or even desirable politically, raises issues as to equality among Europeans, and questions the very meaning of giving substance to EU-wide citizenship by granting social rights at EU level.

IV. Recommendations

The enforcement of social rights merits specific attention and procedures, essentially because they can be easily ignored or eroded in a context of asymmetrical power relations between employers and workers, finance and labour ministries, competitiveness and social protection. Several routes could be followed simultaneously to prevent rights being ineffective on the ground.

1. Improve monitoring and data collection.

It seems especially important to generate evidence about the effectiveness of rights on the ground across 27 countries. This could be organised via systematic reporting of the unions (possibly in the framework of European work councils) about situations where rights are ineffective, notably because workers are unaware of their rights. Trade union research

institutes and/or research departments at both national and EU levels could conduct systematic and concerted analysis of the enforcement of the rights introduced under the EPSR.

2. Keep the enforcement of social rights high on the agenda.

The existence of such data could tap into more politically oriented action to address the revealed gaps in enforcement.

The European Economic and Social Committee could be granted such a role in monitoring the effectiveness of social rights. With members in the groups of Employers, Workers and other activities being close to local and sectoral realities, the EESC seems well placed to build on existing evidence and put together a yearly Report on the Effectiveness of Social Rights. This could be endorsed by the European Parliament (e.g. through an own initiative report) and delivered at the Tripartite Social Summit, the EU Social Forum, and other relevant fora.

The purpose of keeping the issue on the political agenda should be to stimulate debate and compromise among political and social actors about where to draw the line between, on the one hand, avoiding a “one size fits all” approach in a diverse landscape of social policy institutions, and, on the other, maintaining the principle of equality among all Europeans, regardless of where they were born or live.

3. Enable strategic litigation.

Trade unions and other social stakeholders could be further encouraged to use strategic litigation to contest uncompliant transposition and implementation of EU labour law.

Special attention could be granted to whether the existing provisions exhibit an *effet utile*, i.e. whether they help achieve the aim pursued by the legislator.

If the absence of effectiveness is not a result of failing transposition at national level, attention should be paid to the quality and specificity of EU law at the adoption stage. Ultimately, we argue that assessment of the *effet utile* should be a full component of the EU's better regulation agenda.

4. Strengthen administrative cooperation.

While the judicial route should only be considered as a last resort, the effectiveness of social rights can be best guaranteed by effective multi-level administrative cooperation.

Consideration should be given to proposals made by EU labour law scholars to strengthen provisions in EU law regarding administrative cooperation and capacity.

These can include a possible Horizontal Enforcement Directive harmonising existing enforcement devices and adapting them to labour law, or expansion of the mandate of the European Labour Agency to matters beyond the strict realm of cross-border issues ensuing from free movement.

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